

A ‘Systemic’ Model of a Mind-Body Interaction

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Abstract:

This paper shows that, by using a “systemic” mind theory and a formal model initially proposed by Neisser, it is possible to formally represent the mind-body communication processes as they are expressed within the psychoanalytic environment. In this paper, mathematical models of neural networks are used to demonstrate that Neisser’s hypothesis is reinforced if a temporal evolution appears. On the contrary, additional neurophysiological mechanisms

must be postulated to show the differences between primary and secondary processes.

Keywords: *Neural Network, Connectionistic Model, Neisser's model, Mind-body interactions, Mind Theories.*

Introduction

This work aims to demonstrate how to lay the foundations for a mathematical representation of the processes of mind-body interaction, using a theory of the mind of a systemic type and formalizing a model initially presented by Neisser (1963). This circumstance might suggest that in the distant future, this field of study could be part of the hypothetico-deductive sciences, even if we now limit ourselves to very general and abstract considerations.

A Short Account of Traditional Mind Theories

In psychology, behavior is generally explained by reference to mental states, operations, and processes. The difficulty lies in formulating these implications in clear terms. Traditional theories of how the mind works can be divided into three categories: dualistic theories, materialistic theories, and functionalism (Fodor, 1981).

The dualistic definition defines the mind as a non-physical substance (Grankvist, Kajonius &

Persson, 2016; Moreira-Almeida, Araujo & Cloninger, 2018; Maung, 2019). The main difficulty with such a theory is its inability to account for causal interaction. Moreover, it is still being determined how a non-physical mind can give rise to physical effects, without breaking the laws of conservation of mass, energy, and momentum. However, considering the current state of our knowledge, this is a conception that cannot be refuted and does not correspond to the principles of contemporary scientific theory (Hebb, 1980).

The alternative is the dualistic definition, where mind and substance do not fundamentally differ, but are rather different forms of the same substance; in practice, all mental states, properties, processes, and operations are, in principle, identical to physical states, properties, processes and operations. One theory, however, that has succeeded in making sense of the causal and relational nature of the mental is Functionalism (Fodor, 1981).

Functionalism is based on the distinction drawn by computer science between the hardware of a system and its software: the psychology of a

system, such as a human being or a machine, does not depend on what it is composed of (neurons or chips), but on how its components are organised. According to this approach, a mental state would be defined by its causal relationships with other mental states (Berrios, 2018).

At this point, it is interesting to describe the mind-body interaction from the point of view of "Systems Theory"; in other words, to know what happens when a system becomes enormously complex, such as the nervous system. In this case, it is clearly tempting to describe the mind as a global entity that emerges from the local physical interactions between the components of the system itself (Ricciardi, Umezawa, 1967; Guazzo, 1987). To demonstrate the existence of the mind and its relations with the body, it becomes essential to exhibit effective models that show how a complex system, such as a neural network, possesses properties of spontaneous self-organization. Such models should promote collective behaviors capable, in turn, of influencing the activity of the whole system (Scheffel, 2019).

In this context, Neisser's model, which proposed a particular type of self-organisation, is particularly interesting.

The Model

Neisser (1963) considers human thought as multiple activities characterized by independent thought processes. However, one process prevails over the others, giving rise to a main sequence corresponding to the ordinary course of consciousness. It may or may not be directly influenced by the other processes that take place simultaneously.

These hypotheses also have a neurophysiological implication: they imply that in a neural network, such as the human brain, which is subjected to external stimuli, sooner or later areas are formed in which external stimuli can exert their influence only indirectly, alongside other areas in which, instead, the same stimuli are processed in an orderly way, provoking well-organised responses that lead to a specific goal. Thus, in a

generic neural network subject to external stimuli of a certain regularity, areas of both types should form spontaneously (Guazzo, 1987).

Since it is not possible to directly use data of a neurophysiological nature to verify the validity of these hypotheses, mathematical models of the theory of neural networks are used (Guazzo, 1987, 1991); that is, if at the level of these models, a temporal evolution is observed in the way indicated by Neisser, his hypothesis acquires greater credibility.

A fundamental point of Neisser's model is the hypothesis that different phases in brain activities co-occur. This suggests that these phases should be identified with spatially distinct neuronal activity areas (Böhm, Faltermier, Brawanski & Lang, 2013).

To study this mathematical model of the neural network that is a three-dimensional structure, we simplify the situation by referring to two different types of neural networks: one-dimensional and two-dimensional.

Description of the One-Dimensional Model

Consider a neural fiber conducting impulses and regular stimulation, periodical in time. Suppose that a series of nervous impulses run through the fiber and denote with $t_n(x)$ the instant the n -th impulse goes through the point x placed along the fiber. Furthermore, we indicate with $R(x)$ the refractory period in the point x (even this period varies when x varies) and introduce a quantity $\varphi_n(x)$, called the refractory phase, defined by Fomin and Berkinblitt (1975):

$$\varphi_n(x) = \min \left\{ \frac{t_n(x) - t_{n-1}(x)}{R(x)} \right\} \quad (1)$$

which satisfies the following equation:

$$\frac{d\varphi_n(x)}{d(x)} = \frac{1}{R(x)} \left[\frac{1}{v(\varphi_n(x))} - \frac{1}{v(\varphi_{n-1}(x))} - \frac{dR(x)}{d(x)} \varphi_n(x) \right] \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, if the nervous fibre is periodically simulated at the free end by an external stimulus

of period T , we can demonstrate that the time between the passage of two subsequent impulses for the point x is given by:

$$t_n(x) - t_{n-1}(x) = T + \int_0^x \left[\frac{1}{v(\varphi_n(\xi))} - \frac{1}{v(\varphi_{n-1}(\xi))} \right] d\xi \quad (3)$$

where $v(\varphi_n)$, the velocity of propagation of the n -th impulse, is a function of φ_n . A plausible form of $v(\varphi_n)$ is:

$$v(\varphi_n(x)) = \frac{K}{\varphi_n R(x)} \quad (4)$$

Now we choose $R(x) = R_0 + \beta x$ with the initial condition:

$$\varphi_0(x) = \frac{T}{R_0 + \beta x} \quad (5)$$

by substituting (5) into Eqn. (2) we find:

$$\varphi_n(x) = (R_0 + \beta x)^{-1} \exp\left(\frac{x}{K}\right) \left[\int \varphi_{n-1}(x)(R_0 + \beta x) \left(-\frac{1}{K}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{x}{K}\right) dx + C \right] \quad (6)$$

Let us assume:

$$\varphi_{n-1}(x) = \frac{T}{(R_0 + \beta x)} \quad (7)$$

then, by a direct substitution of (7) into (6) we will obtain:

$$\varphi_n(x) = \frac{\left[T + C \exp\left(\frac{x}{K}\right) \right]}{(R_0 + \beta x)} \quad (8)$$

with $C=0$, Eqn. (8) becomes:

$$\varphi_n(x) = \frac{T}{(R_0 + \beta x)} = \varphi_{n-1}(x) \quad (9)$$

Besides, (5) shows that the condition (7) is verified for $n = 0$; Eqn. (9) tells us that it is verified for every value of n ; trivial substitution in (3) gives the result:

$$t_n(x) - t_{n-1}(x) = T \quad (10)$$

for every value of n . This result implies that the formation of partly distinct regions is not detected.

Choose, now, the initial conditions of the type:

$$\varphi_n(0) = \frac{T}{R_0} \quad (11.a)$$

$$\varphi_0(x) = \frac{T}{(R_0 + \beta x)} + \alpha x \quad (11.b)$$

therefore:

$$\varphi_0 = \frac{\left[\alpha \beta x^2 + (\alpha R_0 + 2\alpha \beta K)x + 2\alpha \beta K^2 + \alpha R_0 K + T - (\alpha K^2 R_0 + 2\alpha \beta K^3) \exp\left(\frac{x}{K}\right) \right]}{(R_0 + \beta x)} \quad (12)$$

then $\varphi_n(x) \neq \varphi_{n-1}(x)$ and by a substitution in (3), we have the formation of partly distinct internal region.

Our considerations suggest that partly distinct regions are formed in a general nervous net submitted to external stimuli with a certain regularity (Guazzo, 1987; 1991).

Description of the Two-Dimensional Model

Now, we consider a two-dimensional nervous fiber (defined only in the positive quadrant). Define a function $f(x,y)$ such that its value in the point of coordinate x and y gives the period of

the stimulus that operates in the point of the edge of the coordinates (x,0) and (0,y). Besides, suppose that a series of nervous impulses run through the fiber and denote with the symbol $t_n(x,y)$ the instant in which the n-th impulse arrives at the point of coordinate (x,y) and with $t_{n-1}(x,y)$ the instant in which the (n-1)-th impulse arrives at (x,y). We indicate with $R(x,y)$ the *refractory period* and with $\varphi_n(x,y)$ the *refractory phase* defined by (Guazzo, 1991):

$$\varphi_n(x,y) = \min \left\{ \frac{t_n(x,y) - t_{n-1}(x,y)}{R(x,y)}, 1 \right\} \quad (13)$$

Suppose that the velocity of propagation of the n-th impulse, indicated with v_n is a function of φ_n , that is we have:

$$v_n = v_n(\varphi_n(x,y)) \quad (14)$$

and explicitly:

$$v_x = v_x(\varphi_n(x,y)) \quad (15.a)$$

$$v_y = v_y(\varphi_n(x,y)) \quad (15.b)$$

Assuming that the fibre is stimulated at the edge by an external stimulus of period $f(x,y)$, it can be shown that the time between the passage of two subsequent impulses for the point (x,y) is given by:

$$t_n(x,y) - t_{n-1}(x,y) = f(x,y) + \int_0^x \left[\frac{1}{v_x(\varphi_n(\xi,y))} - \frac{1}{v_x(\varphi_{n-1}(\xi,y))} \right] d\xi + \int_0^y \left[\frac{1}{v_y(\varphi_n(x,\eta))} - \frac{1}{v_y(\varphi_{n-1}(x,\eta))} \right] d\eta \quad (16)$$

Utilizing (13) and (14) we can deduce directly the differential equation which governs $\varphi_n(x,y)$, that is:

$$R \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_n}{\partial x \partial y} + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{v_y^2(\varphi_n)} \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial \varphi_n} \right) \frac{\partial \varphi_n}{\partial x} + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{v_x^2(\varphi_n)} \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial \varphi_n} \right) \frac{\partial \varphi_n}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 R}{\partial x \partial y} = \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{1}{v_y^2(\varphi_{n-1})} \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial \varphi_{n-1}} \frac{\partial \varphi_{n-1}}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{v_x^2(\varphi_{n-1})} \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial \varphi_{n-1}} \frac{\partial \varphi_{n-1}}{\partial y} \quad (17)$$

in which $R = \text{constant}$ and the function $\varphi_n(x,y)$ satisfies the initial conditions:

$$\varphi_n(0,y) = \frac{f(0,y)}{R(0,y)} \quad (18.a)$$

$$\varphi_n(x,0) = \frac{f(x,0)}{R(x,0)} \quad (18.b)$$

In order to utilize these equations concretely, we choose an explicit form of the functions (15.a) and (15.b) which become:

$$v_x = v_y = \frac{K}{K\varphi} \quad (19)$$

Thus, the equation (17) for φ_1 , considering $\varphi_0 = \text{constant}$, takes on the form:

$$K \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_1}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (20)$$

A possible solution of the equation (20) is the constant solution (with φ_1 of co-ordinate (0,y) and (x,0)):

$$\varphi_1(x,y) = \frac{f}{R} \quad (21)$$

in which $f = f_1 = f_2 = \text{constant}$.

Substituting the solution of (20) in (16), we have:

$$t_1(x,y) = f + \left[\frac{K}{f} - \frac{K}{R\varphi_0} \right] x + \left[\frac{K}{f} - \frac{K}{R\varphi_0} \right] y \quad (22)$$

This result implies that the formation of partly distinct regions is detected. Another possible solution of equation (20) is:

$$\varphi_1(x,y) = e^{a\left(\frac{x+y}{ka-1}\right)} \quad (23)$$

which substituted into (16), shows the formation of partly distinct internal regions (Guazzo, 1991).

Now choose φ_0 so that it satisfies the conditions:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_0}{\partial x} = A\varphi_0 \quad (24.a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_0}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (24.b)$$

in this case the equation (17) assumes the form:

$$K \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_1}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial y} = A\varphi_0 \quad (25)$$

The solution of (25) is given by:

$$\varphi(x,y) = \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}} e^{\frac{y}{4x}} \sqrt{y}}{2\sqrt{\tau}} + L^{-1} \left[\frac{\alpha \xi (K-4) + (\beta K - 4A)}{\xi(4\xi - K\xi^2)} \right] + e^{-\sqrt{\frac{4\xi}{K} - \xi^2} y} \quad (26)$$

Substituting (26) into (16) we have the formation of partly distinct regions (Guazzo, 1991).

Conclusion

The arguments we have used so far are certainly not enough to the general validity of Neisser's hypothesis; it would be necessary to examine a more significant number of cases or resolve the model's differential equations directly, which is much more difficult. Moreover, to have at least an abstract and formalized complete description of the mind-body communication processes, it

would be necessary to involve the feedback, as discussed at the beginning, among the results of the actions provoked by the secondary-sequential processes and activity of the neural network. At present, this aspect is the object of both theoretical studies and computer simulations. However, the techniques employed in this work allow, in principle, to construct a formalized theory of the mind-body communication processes capable of precise deductions and experimental controls. At present, this seems to be the best way to surmount the severe methodological problems that, from its beginnings, have tormented scientific psychology.

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